

COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING APPROACH IN TEACHING ENGLISH

Kurbanbaeva Mirigul

student of Foreign Languages Faculty, NSPI.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10779274>

Abstract. *The origins of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) are to be found in the changes in the British language teaching tradition dating from the late 1960s. Until then, Situational Language represented the major British approach to teaching English as a foreign language. In Situational Language Teaching, language was taught by practicing basic structures in meaningful situation-based activities.*

Key Words: *Linguistic Theory of Communication, Language Acquisition, Second Language Acquisition, Grammatical Knowledge.*

КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *Истоки коммуникативного преподавания языка (CLT) можно найти в изменениях в британской традиции преподавания языка, начиная с конца 1960-х годов. До этого ситуационный язык представлял собой основной британский подход к преподаванию английского языка как иностранного. В рамках ситуационного преподавания языка язык преподавал путем отработки базовых структур в значимых ситуативно-ориентированных действиях.*

Ключевые слова: *лингвистическая теория коммуникации, овладение языком, овладение вторым языком, грамматические знания.*

Introduction. Communicative language teaching (CLT) is an approach to language teaching that emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of study. CLT emerged in the 1970s as a reaction to the perceived shortcomings of traditional grammar-translation language teaching methods. Traditional methods focused on teaching grammar and vocabulary in isolation, with little emphasis on the communicative use of the language. CLT, on the other hand, focuses on the development of students' ability to communicate effectively in real-life situations.

The teacher in a communicative language classroom acts as a guide or facilitator and students engage in class activities to learn the language. Development of Language Teaching The communicative approach in language teaching starts from a theory of language as communication.

The goal of language teaching is to develop what Hymes referred to as "communicative competence." Hymes coined this term in order to contrast a communicative view of language and Chomsky's theory of competence. Chomsky held that linguistic theory is concerned primarily with an ideal speaker-listener in a completely homogeneous speech community, who knows its language perfectly and is unaffected by such grammatically irrelevant conditions as memory limitation, distractions, shifts of attention and interest, and errors (random or characteristic) in applying his knowledge of the language in actual performance.

For Chomsky, the focus of linguistic theory was to characterize the abstract abilities speakers possess that enable them to produce grammatically correct sentences in a language.

Hymes held that such a view of linguistic theory was sterile, that linguistic theory needed to be seen as part of a more general theory incorporating communication and culture. Hymes's theory of communicative competence was a definition of what a speaker needs to know in order to be communicatively competent in a speech community. [11:235]

In Hymes's view, a person who acquires communicative competence acquires both knowledge and ability for language use with respect to

1. Whether (and to what degree) something is formally possible;
2. Whether (and to what degree) something is feasible in virtue of the means of implementation available;
3. Whether (and to what degree) something is appropriate (adequate, happy, successful) in relation to a context in which it is used and evaluated;
4. Whether (and to what degree) something is in fact done, actually performed, and what it is doing entails.

In a number of influential books and papers, a second element is the task principle:

Activities in which language is used for carrying out meaningful tasks promote learning.

A third element is the meaningfulness principle: Language that is meaningful to the learner supports the learning process. Learning activities are consequently selected according to how well they engage the learner in meaningful and authentic language use (rather than merely mechanical practice of language patterns). These principles, we suggest, can be inferred from CLT practices.

They address the conditions needed to promote second language learning, rather than the processes of language acquisition. More recent accounts of Communicative Language Teaching, however, have attempted to describe theories of language learning processes that are compatible with the communicative approach. Savignon surveys second language acquisition research as a source for learning theories and considers the role of linguistic, social, cognitive, and individual variables in language acquisition. [11:76]

Other theorists (e.g., Stephen Krashen, who is not directly associated with Communicative Language Teaching) have developed theories cited as compatible with the principles of CLT.

Krashen sees acquisition as the basic process involved in developing language proficiency and distinguishes this process from learning. Acquisition refers to the unconscious development of the target language system as a result of using the language for real communication.

Learning is the conscious representation of grammatical knowledge that has resulted from instruction, and it cannot lead to acquisition. It is the acquired system that we call upon to create utterances during spontaneous language use. The learned system can serve only as a monitor of the output of the acquired system. [3]

Krashen and other second language acquisition theorists typically stress that language learning comes about through using language communicatively, rather than through practicing language skills Johnson and Littlewood consider an alternative learning theory that they also see as compatible with CLT—a skill-learning model of learning. According to this theory, the acquisition of communicative competence in a language is an example of skill development. [4:541]

This involves both a cognitive and a behavioral aspect: The cognitive aspect involves the internalization of plans for creating appropriate behavior. For language use, these plans derive

mainly from the language system — they include grammatical rules, procedures for selecting vocabulary, and social conventions governing speech. The behavioral aspect involves the automation of these plans so that they can be converted into fluent performance in real time. This occurs mainly through practice in converting plans into performance. This theory thus encourages an emphasis on practice as a way of developing communicative skills.

Communicative Principles

1. Language learning is learning to communicate using the target language.
2. The language used to communicate must be appropriate to the situation, the roles of the speakers, the setting and the register. The learner needs to differentiate between a formal and an informal style.
3. Communicative activities are essential.
Activities should be presented in a situation or context and have a communicative purpose. Typical activities of this approach are: games, problem-solving tasks, and role-play. There should be information gap, choice and feedback involved in the activities.
4. Learners must have constant interaction with and exposure to the target language.
5. Development of the four macro skills — speaking, listening, reading and writing — is integrated from the beginning, since communication integrates the different skills.
6. The topics are selected and graded regarding age, needs, level, and students' interest.
7. Motivation is central. Teachers should raise students' interest from the beginning of the lesson.
8. The role of the teacher is that of a guide, a facilitator or an instructor.
9. Trial and error is considered part of the learning process.
10. Evaluation concerns not only the learners' accuracy but also their fluency.

Communicative Features

1. Meaning is paramount.
2. Dialogues, if used, enter around communicative functions and are not normally memorized.
3. Contextualization is a basic premise. (Meaning cannot be understood out of context. Teachers using this approach will present a grammar topic in a meaningful context.
Example: If the new topic to teach is Present Continuous, the teacher will not mime the action of 'walking' and ask: What am I doing? I am walking. Instead, the teacher will show, say, pictures of her last trip and tell the students something like: I have pictures of my vacation. Look, in the picture I am with my friends. We are having lunch at a very expensive restaurant. In this other picture, we are swimming at the beach.
4. Language learning is learning to communicate and effective communication is sought. (When learners are involved in real communication, their natural strategies for language acquisition will be used, and this will allow them to learn to use the language.)
5. Drilling may occur, but peripherally.
6. Comprehensible pronunciation is sought.
7. Translation may be used where students need or benefit from it.
8. Reading and writing can start from the first day.

9. Communicative competence is the desired goal (i.e., the ability to use the linguistic system effectively and appropriately).

10. Teachers help learners in any way that motivates them to work with the language.

11. Students are expected to interact with other people, either in the flesh, through pair and group work, or in their writings.

Communicative Approaches

As the language theories underlying the Audio-lingual method and the Situational method were questioned by prominent linguists like Chomsky during the 1960s, a new trend of language teaching paved its way into classrooms. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), which is an approach to the teaching of second and foreign languages, emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of learning a language. It is also referred to as “Communicative Approach”. Historically, CLT has been seen as a response to the Audio-Lingual Method (ALM), and as an extension or development of the Notional-Functional Syllabus. Task-based language learning, a more recent refinement of CLT, has gained considerably in popularity.

Structuralism And Behaviorism The theories underlying the audio-lingual method and the situational language teaching were widely criticized during the 1960s. Noam Chomsky, for instance, rejected the structuralism view of language and demonstrated that there is a distinction between performance and competence. The goal of the linguist is to study the linguistic competence native speakers are endowed with. He also showed, rightly, that structuralism and behaviorism were unable to account for one fundamental aspect of language, namely the creativity and uniqueness of individual sentences.

A child is able to produce an infinite number of sentences that s/he has never encountered.

This makes the factors of imitation, repetition and habit formation weak arguments to account for any language learning theory. Proficiency of Communicative The increasing interdependency between the European countries necessitated a need for a greater effort to teach adults the principal languages of the continent. New goals were set in language teaching profession:

The paramount importance of communication aspects of language.

The increasing interest in meaningful learning. c. The growing centrality of the learner in teaching processes. d. The subordinate importance of structural teaching of language. Notional language Applied linguists and philosophers addressed another fundamental dimension of language: the functional and communicative potential of language. The speech act theory showed that we do something when we speak a language. We use language

- ✓ to get things,
- ✓ to control behavior,
- ✓ to create interaction with others,
- ✓ to express personal feelings,
- ✓ to learn,
- ✓ to create a world of imagination,
- ✓ to communicate information.

Besides applied linguists emphasized a teaching of language based on communicative proficiency rather than mastery of structures. Instead of describing the core of language through

traditional concepts of grammar and vocabulary, they attempted to show the systems of meaning underlying the communicative use of language. They described two kinds of meanings.

Notional categories: concepts such as time, sequence; quantity, location, frequency.

Functional categories: requests offers, complaints, invitation ... In other words, a “notion” is a particular context in which people communicate. A “function” is a specific purpose for a speaker in a given context. For example, the “notion,” of shopping requires numerous language “functions,” such as asking about prices or features of a product and bargaining.

Language Competence

For Chomsky the focus of linguistics was to describe the linguistic competence that enables speakers to produce grammatically correct sentences. Dell Hymes held, however, that such a view of linguistic theory was sterile and that it failed to picture all the aspects of language. He advocated the need of a theory that incorporate communication competence. It must be a definition of what a speaker needs to know in order to be communicatively competent in a speech community.

- ✓ Grammatical competence: refers to what Chomsky calls linguistic competence.
- ✓ Sociolinguistic competence: refers to an understanding of the social context in which communication takes place (role relationships, shared beliefs and information between participants ...)
- ✓ Discourse competence: refers to the interpretation of individual message elements in terms of their interconnectedness and how meaning is represented in relationship to the entire discourse or text.
- ✓ Strategic competence: refers to the coping strategies that participants use to initiate terminate, maintain, repair and redirect communication Learning Theory According to the communicative approach, in order for learning to take place, emphasis must be put on the importance of these variables:
 - ✓ Communication: activities that involve real communication promote learning.
 - ✓ Tasks: An activity in which language is used to carry out meaningful tasks supports the learning process.

Meaning: language that is meaningful and authentic to the learner boosts learning. Stephen Krashen later advocated in his language learning theory that there should be a distinction between learning and acquiring. He sees acquisition as the basic process involved in developing language proficiency and distinguishes this process from learning. Acquisition is an unconscious process that involves the naturalistic development of language proficiency while learning is the conscious internalization of the rules of language. It results in explicit knowledge about the forms of language and the ability to verbalize this knowledge. Learning according to Krashen cannot lead to acquisition. Advantages of Teaching. There are many advantages in teaching according to the communicative approach:

CLT is a holistic approach. It does not focus only on the traditional structural syllabus. It takes into consideration communicative dimension of language. [6:279]

CLT provides vitality and motivation within the classroom.

CLT is a learner-centered approach. It capitalizes on the interests and needs of the learner. [6:279]

In a world where communication of information and information technology has broken new considerable ground, CLT can play an important role in education. **Conclusion.** In sum up CLT is the best considered an approach rather than a method.

Thus although a reasonable degree of theoretical consistency can be discerned at the levels of language and learning theory, at the levels of design and procedure there is much greater room for individual interpretation and variation than most methods permit. It could be that one version among the various proposals for syllabus models, exercise types, and classroom activities may gain wider approval in the future, giving Communicative Language Teaching a status similar to other teaching methods. On the other hand, divergent interpretations might lead to homogeneous subgroups.

Communicative Language Teaching appeared at a time when British language teaching was ready for a paradigm shift. Situational Language Teaching was no longer felt to reflect a methodology appropriate for the seventies and beyond. CLT appealed to those who sought a more humanistic approach to teaching, one in which the interactive processes of communication received priority., language specialists, publishers, as well as institutions, such as the British Council.

REFERENCES

1. Bax, Stephen (2003-07-01). "The end of CLT: a context approach to language teaching". *ELT Journal*. 57 (3): 278–287. doi:10.1093/elt/57.3.278. ISSN 0951-0893.
2. Brandl, Klaus (2007). *Communicative Language Teaching in Action: Putting Principles to Work*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Phil Miller. pp. 284–297. ISBN 9780131579064.
3. Canale, M.; Swain, M. (1980-03-01). "Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing ". *Applied Linguistics*. I (1): 1– 47. doi:10.1093/applin/i.1.1. ISSN 0142-6001.
4. Littlewood, William. *Communicative language teaching: An introduction*. Cambridge University Press, 1981, pp. 541-545
5. Mitchell, Rosamond (1988). *Communicative Language Teaching in Practice*. Great Britain: Centre for Information on Language Teaching and Research. pp. 23–24, 64–68. ISBN 978-0948003875.
6. Nunan, David (1991-01-01). "Communicative Tasks and the Language Curriculum". *TESOL Quarterly*. 25 (2): 279–295. CiteSeerX 10.1.1.466.1153. doi:10.2307/3587464. JSTOR 3587464.
7. Richards, Jack C. *Communicative language teaching today*. SEAMEO Regional Language Centre, 2005.
8. Richards, Jack; Rodgers, Theodore (2014). *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching (3rd Edition)*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. pp. 23–24, 84–85. ISBN 978-1-107-67596-4.
9. Richards, Jack (2006). *Communicative Language Teaching Today*. USA: Cambridge University Press. pp. 14–21. ISBN 9780521925129.
10. Ridge, Elaine (1992). "Communicative language teaching: Time for review?". *Stellenbosch Papers in Linguistics Plus*. 21. doi:10.5842/21-0-533. ISSN 2224-3380.

11. Savignon, Sandra J. (1987-09-01). "Communicative language teaching". *Theory into Practice*. 26 (4): 235–242. doi:10.1080/00405848709543281. ISSN 0040-5841.
12. Swan, Michael (1985-01-01). "A critical look at the Communicative Approach (1)". *ELT Journal*. 39 (1): 2–12. doi:10.1093/elt/39.1.2. ISSN 0951-0893.
13. Swan, Michael (1985-04-01). "A Critical look at the Communicative Approach (2)". *ELT Journal*. 39 (2): 76–87. doi:10.1093/elt/39.2.76. ISSN 0951-0893.